

ISic1653

I.Sicily inscription 1653

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 15592

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2 : mm

Text

0. □

1. Ἐτελεύτη

2. σεν ἢ καλῆ[ς] μνή

3. μης Περειρίνα

4. τῶν Βολιμαρίω[ν]

5. τῆ πρό δ εἰδῶν

6. Νόβεμβρίων

7. ὑπατίπα

8. Ἐρκουλιάνου

9. καὶ εἴῃ τις ἀπό

10. Ἀνατολῆς

11. μενυθήσεται

Apparatus

Text after Orsi 1896

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645091

PHI 331250

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 34.0983

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.97

Orsi, P. 1896. Gli scavi a S. Giovanni a Siracusa. *Römische Quartalschrift für christliche Alterthumskunde und für Kirchengeschichte*. 10: 1-59. At 49 no.84

Wessel, C. 1989. Inscriptiones Graecae Christianae Veteres Occidentis. *Inscriptiones Christianae Italiae*. Bari. At 127

Feissel, D. 1984. Notes d'épigraphie chrétienne (VII). *Bulletin de Correspondance Hellénique*. 108: 545-579. At 567 n.124

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 28 n.117

Licensed under a Creative Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1653. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354735>